

NATIONAL CADET CORPS (NCC) TRAINING: AN ALTERNATIVE TO COMPULSORY MILITARY TRAINING IN INDIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17079702>

Published Date: 08-September-2025

Abstract: During the World Wars, many countries resorted to conscription, to rapidly increase the strength of the armed forces, to deal with the belligerent neighbours. Over a period of time, majority of the countries have stopped conscription as it causes a huge drain on the economy. But now, some of the nations such as Ukraine, do adopt conscription as they face the heat from Russian invasion. Since Independence, India did not follow any kind of conscription. Indian Army has always been an army of volunteers. Conscription not only builds physical strength but also builds nationalism and imbibes the spirit of patriotism. Some countries carry out some form of conscription such as Compulsory Military Training (CMT) to induce patriotism and build nationalism among the youth. In India, over a million students do undergo NCC training every year. But there is hardly any literature on the effects of NCC on nation building, especially in colleges running NCC in the southern India. The present study was conducted during December of 2022 with a sample of cadets, drawn from colleges of Tamil Nadu and analysed whether present NCC was a cheaper alternative method instead of the CMT, to impart nationalism and patriotism to the youth of the country. 368 NCC cadets and 368 Non NCC College students were contacted for gathering information for this study. This study found that the NCC training developed patriotic qualities such as character, selflessness and nationalism qualities, which are the main focus areas in CMT.

Keywords: Compulsory Military Training (CMT), Conscription, Nationalism, Selflessness, Character, Patriotism, Soft skills, National Cadet Corps, NCC, Team Work, Self Confidence, Self-Reliance, Camaraderie, Leadership, Human Resource, Youth Organisation, National Integration, Employment Qualities.

I. INTRODUCTION

Compulsory Military Training (CMT), otherwise called Conscription and also known as 'the draft' is the mandatory enlistment of people in their national armed forces. The modern system of Universal National Conscription for young men, dates back to the French Revolution in the 1790s, where it was the basis of a large and powerful military. During the World Wars, many European countries resorted to conscription as they faced constant threat from opposing military alliances. Conscription helped such countries to increase the strength of national armed forces quickly and have mass armies at their disposal. But by the end of the Second World War, and even more so after the end of the Cold War, majority of democratic countries began to abolish, formally or informally, their conscription system which seemed unnecessary in peaceful times.

Between 1990 and 2013, many countries in the European Union decided to abandon the draft. At present, only a handful of the countries still follow conscription in one form or the other like Russia, North Korea, Iran, Israel, Brazil, Turkey South Korea, Cuba, Switzerland, Sweden and Singapore. It is to be noted that other than rapid build-up of strength, the military training also brings its own benefits. Many studies have brought out the fact that the military training induces national unity and imparts nationalism and patriotism to the youth. Recently UAE introduced CMT to infuse discipline to the youth. India does not follow the CMT and its army remains a volunteer army. **Nandhene K. (2018)** refers to the discussion held, while drafting the constitution by the members of the constituent assembly, when Dr BR Ambedkar pointed out that the people have a duty to support the Government (country) and compulsory military service is nothing but asking the people to fulfil that duty. All members of constituent assembly unanimously agreed that conscription is not prohibited under the fundamental rights but CMT was not included in the provision of the constitution. Though CMT was not included in the law, the Constitution does enable the States to impose compulsory service for public purpose and while imposing such services, the States shall not make any discrimination on grounds of religion, race, caste or class or any of them. The former Defence Minister, Shri Arun Jaitley, in a written reply to Shri CS Putta Raju in Lok Sabha on 23 July 2014, said that the Government of India is not in favour of making military training compulsory to all the youth of the country as it may lead to militarisation of youth and also the country does not have adequate number of training facilities to train all the youth of the country. The likely benefits of imparting military training to all the youth will not be commensurate with the expenditure towards such an effort. Against this background, an attempt has been made in this study, to analyse methods to impart some form of CMT to the youth of the India, to develop physical fitness as well to impart patriotic qualities.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

a) Studies on Compulsory Military Service

N.Nasr (2021) has quoted Mr Goh, former PM of Singapore, who maintains that “nothing creates loyalty and national consciousness more thoroughly than participation in its defense”. Rongé et al (2019) point out that conscription was followed in Mesopotamia, and “the draft” became a practical way of enrolment after the French Revolution. Conscription appeared to be efficient in increasing national armed forces. It helped the countries to recruit and train the troops in peacetime even before war was declared. N. Nasr (2021) further argues that the non-alignment policy played an important role in Switzerland’s defence strategy. As the country was not aligned, no other country will also help them during their need. Therefore, Switzerland still follows conscription, which is necessary for them to raise an army in quick time in case of war. Alterman & Balboni, (2017), in their report on UAE, discussed the various factors, which contributed to the introduction of conscription in 2014. One was the deeply unsettled regional environment in U.A.E and another was the drive to promote a stronger sense of nationalism. But most of all, the UAE leadership feared that the young Emirati men were becoming soft and physically unfit due to their luxurious lifestyle. The Government introduced a bold constructive program, which combined intensive physical fitness, national education and character education with military training. As on date, the program is running successfully in UAE. Nandhene, K. (2018) in his article debates whether India should go for conscription or not. The author agrees that military service brings about national unity, but he questions whether the nation should go for conscription just for the sake of national unity. It is viewed that there are many organisations such as National Cadet Corps (NCC), which can do the same job without going for compulsory military service. Similar argument was put forth by Brig Kapur (2021) that though compulsory military service imparts a sense of discipline and patriotism, CMT is controversial for a number of reasons, including conscientious objection to military engagements on religious or philosophical grounds and political objection. The author maintains that a middle path could be taken to put the adults through NCC training to achieve the intention of imparting national unity. Lt Gen GS Katoch, (2016), in the Defence and Security Alert strongly asserts that the army led National Cadet Corps is engaged in grooming the youth and helping them to imbibe qualities of discipline, selfless service and the spirit of nationalism.

b) Studies on the Effectiveness of NCC

NCC is a large youth organization, created in 1948, to develop Indian students into better citizens and provide disciplined and reliable personnel to assist the Government, during natural disaster, for conducting social welfare schemes and meeting other emergencies. Elavarasan et al (2020) evaluated the views collated from a sample of 315 NCC cadets and 315 Non NCC college students across six districts of Tamil Nadu. It was found that NCC training significantly improved the leadership qualities. Sinha (1966) evaluated NCC training, in the development of leadership qualities, from the views of a sample of 300 school going students and found that NCC training and development of leadership qualities were positively

correlated. Panigrahi (2009) carried out a study, covering 180 NCC cadets and 180 college students in Orissa. It was found that NCC cadets were more motivated, more risk takers than the other college students. Mohan Kumar (2015) conducted a study on 356 NCC cadets and 356 college students of Tamil Nadu, at Chennai and Puducherry. The study found that NCC students displayed greater national values and love for the country, unity, justice, equality, sociality and brotherhood than that of the college students. Sarkar, U, & Margaj, (2015) conducted a study among 120 NCC cadets and found that NCC cadets acquired more soft skill qualities and exhibited above average soft skill qualities, on a scale of 100. These studies revealed that just as CMT imparts a sense of discipline and patriotism among the soldiers, the NCC training also enabled a person to become disciplined and patriotic.

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

It is obvious from the earlier studies that many nations resort to conscription, to fulfil two major objectives. Firstly, to guard the country by saving it from any imminent threat. Secondly, it helps to infuse nationalistic spirit among the youth of the nation and makes them patriotic and disciplined. Incidentally, India has the second largest standing army in the world and does not need conscription to rapidly increase the strength. However, the conscription raises few important questions. Whether the Indian army can absorb the entire population of students, who are exiting the school every year? Whether the nation can afford the budget which would be required to put all the students through CMT? It is pertinent to refer to a written reply, by the Minister for State for Defence, Mr Ajay Bhatt on 21 Dec 2021, who specified that the strength of Indian armed forces stands at approximately 1.4 million persons on active duty. In another article, which appeared in India.com in 2017, puts the number of school students who appear in 12th exam, was more than one crore. Even if the Government agrees to earmark 10% of 1.4 million soldiers, the army can absorb maximum of 1.4 lakh students every year. If the tenure of their service in the army is for two years, then the Indian army can only accommodate half of 1.4 lakhs i.e. 70 thousand students, which is very small compared to the one crore students who will be passing out of the school every year. This leaves a whopping 99.25% of students who cannot be given military training. Shri Arun Jaitley, the former defence minister of India, already said that it is economically unviable to run a large scale military training. Therefore, it is very clear that India cannot afford to adopt CMT across the entire student population. Now the crux of the question before us is, how to make the young students of the country physically fit as well as impart discipline, nationalism and patriotism within a reasonable cost? Previous research studies clearly show that organisations like NCC impart leadership skills, soft skills with lesser cost and transforms the student into a better citizen. Hence this study to evaluate whether NCC can infuse patriotic spirit among the NCC cadets and fill the gap, arising on account of not imparting CMT to the youth of India.

IV. NEED OF THE STUDY

The study would help to understand whether NCC can fulfil the aspirations of the country, to instil patriotic qualities in the minds of young adults of the country. The study would also help the Government to understand whether NCC can be an alternative to the CMT. The study would also help the Government to formulate policies to strengthen the alternative training such as NCC. Besides, findings of this study would generate empirical data, on the effect of NCC training towards enhancement of patriotic qualities among NCC cadets. Further, the modules of NCC training could be improved, in the light of the findings of this study for the benefit of the Indian nation.

a) Main Objective

The aim of the present study was to assess whether NCC can improve the patriotic qualities like character, selflessness and nationalism, which are necessary for nation building, among the students who undergo NCC training in Tamil Nadu, South India.

b) Sub Objectives

In order to achieve the main aim, this study identified three sub objectives, as follows: -

- i) To assess whether the NCC training promotes the character qualities among NCC cadets or not.
- ii) To study whether NCC training improves selflessness qualities among NCC cadets or not.
- iii) To understand whether NCC training promotes the nationalism qualities among NCC cadets or not.
- iv) To offer suggestions to improve the NCC training with a focus on nation building of India.

V. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The following three null hypotheses were developed and tested in the study.

NH01: There is no improvement in character qualities of NCC Cadets due to NCC training against Non NCC college students.

NH02: There is no improvement in selflessness qualities of NCC Cadets due to NCC training against Non NCC college students.

NH03: There is no improvement in nationalism qualities of NCC Cadets due to NCC training against Non NCC college students

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

a) Source and Collection of Data

This study was based on both primary and secondary data. The required primary data were collected through a survey of 83 colleges, running NCC training, covering 23 districts in Tamil Nadu. The study was carried out in the month of December 2022. The secondary data were collected from various reputed books, journals, related studies and web sites.

b) Sample Population

There were 7360 Senior College Students, who were undergoing NCC training in Central Tamil Nadu (Southern India), across 23 districts, covering 83 colleges. The minimum sample size, required for the study, was calculated by using the Cochran's formula, for a very large population, which is:

$$n_0 = \frac{Z^2 pq}{e^2} = 384$$

where Z = confidence level of 95% i.e. 1.96

p (probability of cadets having patriotism qualities) = 0.5 and q= 1-p

e (margin of error) = 0.05

As the cadet strength was 7360, the above formula was readjusted for a very large population. The sample size was decided by using the following formula:

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{(n_0 - 1)}{N}} = 364$$

where $n_0 = 384$ and $N = 7360$.

The sample population for this study, consisting of 5% (368) of total NCC cadets (7360) undergoing NCC training in Trichy NCC Group of Tamil Nadu, was more than the calculated minimum sample population of 364. In addition, equal number of Non NCC college students, who were keen on responding but who did not get the opportunity to join the NCC, were also selected and included in the sample population. Particular attention was also paid to ensure that the sample numbers were equal among NCC cadets and Non NCC college students. The survey was conducted by circulating a printed questionnaire among the NCC cadets and Non NCC college students. The questionnaire was administered to 368 NCC cadets and 368 Non NCC college students, totalling 736. All the 368 NCC cadets and 307 Non NCC college students fully responded to the questionnaire. Other 61 respondents either did not fully or partly responded. Finally, all the responses of 675 (368 NCC cadets and 307 Non NCC college students) were considered for the analysis of this study.

c) Pilot Study

Before conducting the survey, the sample questionnaire was circulated among 50 respondents. Based on the responses received from them, the schedule was redesigned and the revised schedule, after incorporating the suggestions of the pilot study, was distributed to all the 736 cadets/students for collecting the required information.

d) Variables Used

For the purpose of the study, patriotism qualities were split into three variables namely character, selflessness and nationalism. Each variable was assessed through a set of questions. The assessment questions are similar to assessment tests conducted by the Service Selection Board (SSB), for selecting cadets to National Defence Academy, Indian Military Academy and Officer Training Academy while selecting the officers for defence forces. For the purpose of this study, the character was assessed under five subheads, namely, Extraversion vs Introversion, Agreeableness vs Antagonism, Conscientiousness vs Lack of Direction, Neuroticism vs Emotional Stability, Openness vs Closed to Experience. Selflessness was assessed under two subheads namely Individual Selfless Acts and Organizational Selfless Acts. Nationalism of an individual was assessed under awareness of National Symbols, Civic Participation and Sports Participation. There were 25 questions to assess the character, 10 questions to assess selflessness and 10 questions to assess nationalism. The respondents were asked to rate their responses on a 'Five Point Scale', indicating the extent to which they agreed with each statement. In the survey, the sample respondents had rated each item on a One (Not Important) to Five (Very Important) point scale. The survey results were checked for their reliability, by Cronbach Alpha Test, which reported a value of 0.841.

e) Tools Used

This study used Descriptive Statistics, Comparison of Means, two Sample one tail 't' test, Excel and SPSS software to analyse the patriotism qualities among different sample groups.

VII. ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

The analysis of the impact of NCC training on sample students/cadets in Southern India, is presented as follows: -

- a) Analysis of Demographic Profile of Sample Population.
- b) Assessment of the Character Qualities of NCC Cadets and Non NCC College Students.
- c) Assessment of the Selflessness qualities of NCC Cadets and Non NCC College students.
- d) Assessment of the Nationalism qualities of NCC Cadets and Non NCC College students.
- e) Assessment of Character, Selflessness and Nationalism among the Male and Female NCC cadets.

a) Analysis of Demographic Profile of Sample Population.

Table-1 shows the 'Results of Demographic Profile of Sample Respondents (NCC and Non NCC) in Tamil Nadu, South India. As stated earlier, 368 NCC cadets and 307 non NCC college students responded to the survey perfectly. It is to be noted that the total of 675 perfectly responded respondents consisted of 245 females and 430 males. The analysis of the survey revealed that majority of the sample NCC cadets, reported two or more years of NCC training. Further, out of 675 cadets and non-cadets, 44 belonged to men's colleges and 86 belonged to women's colleges while 545 belonged to co-education colleges. Besides, majority of the sample cadets and non-cadets (434 out of 675) resided in villages and only 241 cadets lived in towns. It was observed from the analysis that large number of respondents' parents (592 out of 675) earned an annual income of less than 6 lakhs per year while 82 parents earned an income between 6 to 12 lakh rupees per year. Only one parent in the entire sample population earned more than 12 lakhs per year, whose ward was a non-cadet. The analysis of professional side of respondents' parents indicated that many parents belonged to agriculture background (267 out of 675) or daily wage labour (211 out of 675) in the agricultural and other related fields. In other words, the bulk of the cadet/student respondents were from poor and agricultural family. Further, majority of NCC cadets preferred to join army while majority of the non NCC college students preferred to join IAS/IPS or take up government job. This revealed that students, who underwent NCC training developed national pride and preferred to join army. The overall analysis of the survey clearly indicated that the sample participant cadets/students belonged to a mixed strata of the society but majority of them were from poor and agricultural family.

Table-1: Results of Demographic Profile of Sample Respondents (NCC and Non NCC) in Tamil Nadu, South India

Type		NCC Cadets	Non NCC College Students	Total
Gender	Female	126	119	245
	Male	242	188	430
	Total	368	307	675
Year of NCC	1st Yr	15	0	15
	2nd Yr	171	0	171
	3rd Yr	182	0	182
	Non NCC	0	307	307
	Total	368	307	675
Type of College	Men's College	30	14	44
	Ladies College	43	43	86
	Co-Ed College	295	250	545
	Total	368	307	675
Place of Residence	Village	251	183	434
	Town or City	117	124	241
	Total	368	307	675
Annual Income	Less than 6 Lakh	327	265	592
	6 Lakh to 12 Lakhs	41	41	82
	More than 12 Lakhs	0	1	1
	Total	368	307	675
Fathers' Occupation	Agriculture	149	118	267
	Labour	125	86	211
	Govt Job	35	50	85
	Business	44	41	85
	Others	15	12	27
	Total	368	307	675
Choice of Profession	Soldier in Armed Forces	38	9	47
	Constable in Police	11	16	27
	Officer in Army	138	14	152
	IAS/IPS	84	80	164
	Govt Job	84	175	259
	Others	13	13	26
	Total	368	307	675

Source: Primary Data

b) Assessment of the Character Qualities of NCC Cadets and Non NCC College Students.

The results of Mean, SD and one tail 't' Test for the character qualities among the sample NCC cadets/ Non NCC students in Tamil Nadu, Southern India are given in **Table-2**. The analysis clearly indicated the mean score of NCC cadets to be 36.341, in respect of character qualities, which was higher than the mean score of 34.500 for Non NCC college students. The overall calculated 't' value for character qualities, under one tail t test, stood at 4.266, which was much higher than the table value of 1.647. Therefore, the null hypothesis (NH₀₁) - **There is no improvement in Character Qualities of NCC Cadets due to NCC Training against Non NCC College Students**, was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. It is understood from the overall analysis that NCC training was useful in building good character among young students. It is suggested that more students are to be encouraged to attend NCC training, which will be useful for them during their employment.

Table-2: The Results of Two Sample t test for Character Qualities of Sample Respondents in Tamil Nadu, South India

Statistical Quantities	NCC Cadets	Non NCC College Students
Mean	36.341	34.500
Variance	31.963	30.210
Standard Error	0.29	0.31
Median	36.20	34.80
Mode	38.00	37.20
Observations	368	307
Kurtosis	10.67	7.98
Skewness	-1.69	-1.52
Confidence Level(95.0%)	0.58	0.62
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	673	
t Stat	4.266	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.000	
t Critical one-tail	1.647	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.000	
t Critical two-tail	1.963	

Source: Collected from primary data and computed by using SPSS

c) Assessment of the Selflessness qualities of NCC Cadets and Non NCC College students.

Table-3 exhibits the results of Mean, SD and one tail 't' Test for selflessness skills, among the sample NCC cadets and non NCC college students of Tamil Nadu, South India. The analysis clearly revealed the mean score to be 41.139, for NCC cadets selflessness qualities, which was higher than the mean score of 38.550 for selfless qualities of Non NCC college students. The overall calculated t value of selflessness skills was at 5.271, which was much higher than the table value of 1.647. Therefore, the null hypothesis (NH_{02}) - **There is no improvement in Selflessness Qualities of NCC Cadets due to NCC training against Non NCC College students**, was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. In other words, NCC training did help the persons to develop qualities of selfless nature, which is one of the important ingredients of patriotism, for which CMT was proposed. Hence steps are to be initiated to attract all students of colleges, to undergo NCC training, to inculcate the qualities of selflessness.

Table-3: The Results of Two Sample t test for Selflessness Qualities of Sample Respondents in Tamil Nadu, South India

Statistical Quantities	NCC Cadets	Non NCC College Students
Mean	41.139	38.550
Variance	34.643	47.203
Standard Error	0.307	0.392
Median	42.000	39.000
Mode	42.000	42.000
Standard Deviation	5.886	6.870
Sample Variance	34.643	47.203
Kurtosis	7.582	6.175
Skewness	-1.676	-1.642
Confidence Level(95.0%)	0.603	0.772
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0.000	
df	673	
t Stat	5.271	

P(T<=t) one-tail	0.000	
t Critical one-tail	1.647	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.000	
t Critical two-tail	1.963	

Source: Collected from Primary Data and computed by using SPSS

d) Assessment of the Nationalism qualities of NCC Cadets and Non NCC College students.

The results of Mean, SD and one tail 't' Test for nationalism qualities, among the sample NCC cadets and Non NCC college students in Tamil Nadu, Southern India, are presented in **Table-4**. It is understood from the analysis that the mean score of 39.467 for NCC cadets, in respect nationalism qualities, was higher than the mean score of 37.306 for Non NCC college students. The overall calculated 't' value of nationalism qualities was at 4.319, which was much higher than the table value of 1.647. Therefore, the null hypothesis (**NH03**) – **There is no improvement in Nationalism qualities of NCC Cadets due to NCC training against Non NCC College students**, was rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted. In other words, NCC training can be an alternative to CMT and the colleges should include NCC training in their curriculum to improve to improve the nationalistic qualities.

Table-4: The Results of Two Sample t test for Nationalism Qualities of Sample Respondents in Tamil Nadu, South India

Statistical Quantities	NCC Cadets	Non NCC College Students
Mean	39.467	37.306
Variance	39.013	45.396
Observations	368.000	307.000
Standard Error	0.326	0.385
Median	40.000	38.000
Mode	42.000	38.000
Standard Deviation	6.246	6.738
Sample Variance	39.013	45.396
Kurtosis	16.151	8.329
Skewness	-2.899	-1.880
Confidence Level(95.0%)	0.640	0.757
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0.000	
df	673	
t Stat	4.319	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.000	
t Critical one-tail	1.647	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.000	
t Critical two-tail	1.963	

Source: Collected through Primary Data and calculated by using SPSS

e) Assessment of Character, Selflessness and Nationalism among the Male and Female NCC Cadets.

The analysis of this survey clearly indicated that NCC training strongly helped the NCC cadets in improving the character, selflessness and nationalism qualities better. An attempt has been made in the study, to compare and find whether there was any difference statistically, in these three qualities, among the male and female cadets within the NCC, who are undergoing the training. The results of Mean, SD and 't' Test for Character, Selflessness and Nationalism Qualities among the male and female sample NCC cadets in Tamil Nadu, Southern India, are given in **Table-5**. As stated earlier, out of 368 NCC Cadets (242 male NCC cadets and 126 female NCC cadets) responded to the study, but the analysis showed minor variations in the mean score of male and female respondents. It was heartening to note that there was no significant difference in the calculated t value in respect of all the three qualities, assessed among male and female respondents. The study proved from the overall analysis that the NCC training was effective in inculcating human skills equally across both the genders. It is to be noted that Non NCC cadets missed these opportunities to improve their character, selflessness and nationalistic qualities.

Table-5: The Results of Two Sample t Test for Character, Selflessness and Nationalism qualities among Male and Female NCC cadets in Tamil Nadu, South India

Patriotism Skills	Statistical Quantities	Male NCC Cadets	Female NCC Cadets
Character	Mean	36.25289	36.511111
	Variance	40.36134	15.983716
	Observations	242	126
	Pooled Variance	32.03565	
	Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
	df	366	
	t Stat	-0.41528	
	P(T<=t) one-tail	0.339091	
	t Critical one-tail	1.649028	
	P(T<=t) two-tail	0.678181	
	t Critical two-tail	1.966467	
Selflessness	Mean	41.03719	41.333333
	Variance	40.55048	23.472
	Observations	242	126
	Pooled Variance	34.71766	
	Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
	df	366	
	t Stat	-0.4575	
	P(T<=t) one-tail	0.32379	
	t Critical one-tail	1.649028	
	P(T<=t) two-tail	0.64758	
	t Critical two-tail	1.966467	
Nationalism	Mean	39.82231	38.785714
	Variance	38.03884	40.489714
	Observations	242	126
	Pooled Variance	38.87588	
	Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
	df	366	
	t Stat	1.513352	
	P(T<=t) one-tail	0.065527	
	t Critical one-tail	1.649028	
	P(T<=t) two-tail	0.131053	
	t Critical two-tail	1.966467	

Source: Collected through Primary Data and calculated by using SPSS

VIII. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The select findings based on the analysis of this study and interaction with NCC officials, are presented below.

- Countries across the world undertake conscription, with the aim of building the strength of army, to face any kind of external aggression rapidly.
- CMT helps to build patriotism and national spirit, in addition to keep the adults physically fit.
- The Indian armed forces have a total strength of approximately 14 lakh combat men.
- Indian army cannot accommodate the entire strength of students, who pass out from the schools, to undertake compulsory military training as it involves huge cost.
- The organisations like NCC, NSS or Red Cross Society could be the alternate means instead of CMT for youth training in India. NCC training is effective in inculcating patriotic qualities among the youth of the nation.

- f) The participants of the study belonged to a mixed strata of the society but majority of sample participants belonged to very poor and agricultural families in the income bracket of less than six lakhs per year.
- g) There was stark contrast in the choice of profession by NCC cadets and Non NCC college students. NCC cadets preferred to join the army while Non NCC Cadets preferred to join IAS/IPS or any other government job.
- h) The study confirmed that the NCC cadets displayed higher degree of patriotic qualities, which include character, selflessness and nationalistic qualities, than the Non NCC college students. The analysis of patriotism between the male and female NCC cadets, showed no significant difference in any of the patriotic qualities between them.
- i) In short NCC training did help in developing patriotic qualities among the NCC cadets than the Non NCC college students.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

In the light of the findings of this study and feedback from NCC officials, some of the important suggestions are summarised below.

a) Suggestions to NCC

- i) Since NCC training helps in developing many human skills among the cadets, which are very essential for the nation building, the NCC should continue to effectively conduct such training across the country and improve character, selflessness and nationalistic qualities, which are the main ingredients of patriotism, among the youth of the nation at schools and colleges.
- ii) There was no significant difference in patriotism qualities between male and female cadets. NCC should continue such training, without any gender bias, in future too as an alternative to CMT.

b) Suggestions to Government

- i) The number of students, who pass out of schools every year, is over one crore, but the strength of army is only 14 lakhs. Hence, all the pass-out students every year cannot be absorbed into army, for the purpose of CMT. It is to be noted that carrying out an exclusive military training is not cost effective and will be a huge burden on the nation.
- ii) Recently, the Indian army has introduced a new scheme called as **AGNIPATH** where eligible candidates will be given a chance to serve the army for a four-year period and then they can leave the army. But due to the limited vacancies, the Agnipath scheme cannot accommodate bulk of the youth of the country and they will miss out on military training which is very important for nation building.
- iii) To achieve the same aim of inculcating patriotism, the Government should look at strengthening the alternative organisations such as NCC, NSS, Red cross etc. to CMT.
- iv) As on date, NCC is imparting training to more than 13 lakh cadets every year. NCC should be strengthened further to train maximum number of youth of the nation, at schools and colleges.

X. CONCLUSION

Military training always brings about a sea change in the minds of the students. It transforms a young boy into a disciplined man and makes him loyal to the flag of the country. Every nation desires to carry out CMT in one form or the other so that trained, loyal manpower is available during emergency. However, conscription has become obsolete and many nations have discontinued it. Many nations are looking for alternative training system like NCC, to mobilise the general public to deal with any crisis. It has become customary to call the army, for dealing with every kind of crisis, which otherwise could be dealt with by the general public, if they are provided adequate training to deal with such emergencies. The public requires structured training to deal with such crisis critical situations. This could happen if the youth were to undergo some form of quasi military training such as NCC where they are trained to deal with emergencies. NCC is one alternative of the future, which has proved its merits in many places and at many times. The Government should seriously think of expanding the NCC and provide the NCC with requisite resources to undertake the same.

XI. SCOPE FOR FURTHER STUDY

- a) Similar study, covering other States of India, would check the efficacy of NCC training.
- b) The future study could be carried out to find out how effective is NCC training to develop other qualities such as citizenship qualities, soft skills and military qualities.
- c) Further studies should be carried out to find out whether NCC cadets were motivated to join the armed forces or did they join the forces due to compulsions of poor economic background.
- d) Further studies could be attempted to find out whether NCC training developed sportsmanship.
- e) The NCC also carries out many Youth Exchange Programs with friendly foreign countries where cadets from foreign countries visit India and attend youth camps with Indian cadets. A study could be undertaken to compare the patriotism of Indian cadets with foreign cadets.

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